

Equity in OA Workshop Report commissioned by

Open Access Scholarly Publishing
Association (OASPA)

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Equity in OA Workshop 4: Report

Background

This fourth workshop in the Equity in OA series took place on 22 June 2023 with librarians, funders, publishers, and other stakeholders.

This workshop built on the [first workshop](#), [second workshop](#), and [third workshop](#) in which participants from a wide array of countries discussed why equity is important, current challenges to global equity, and potential solutions to some of these. This workshop discussed two issues that the earlier workshops in the series identified as barriers to Equity in OA:

- Problems of prestige and perception related to OA.
- Pathways to stable and predictable funding streams to sustain a full transition to OA.

Publisher participants were reminded not to share any information that was private or in any way commercially sensitive. We also asked publishing participants not to explain what their organizations are doing at present, nor what their organizations might/could contemplate doing in the future.

What can OASPA, and its members, do to address problems of prestige and perception related to OA in the research community?

We began with a Sli.do poll asking participants to what extent do you think perceptions about prestige or OA are a barrier to global equity by influencing decisions of where to publish or what to read. 47% percent of the participants think that this is somewhat of a problem and 53% think that it is very much a problem.

The group then discussed:

- How (real and perceived) concerns feed perceptions that OA publishing is undesirable or untrustworthy.
- Whether and how publishers' justifiable pride in high-quality journals (e.g., demonstrated through impact factors or other metrics) contribute to these concerns.

Prestige perceptions are multi-faceted. Participants discussed the many issues that contribute to a perception that OA publishing does not have the prestige of subscription publishing. It was noted that perceptions can be dependent on the discipline and on geography, vary across publishers and titles, and between individuals. There are, however, some consistent themes:

- Open access titles are relatively young and have not had so long to build reputations as prestigious places to publish within their disciplines.
- Tied to this is a “prestige economy” for promotion and tenure where impact factors or other metrics matter and lead researchers to publish in certain venues.

- Launching an open access journal can sometimes require less upfront investment and risk than launching a subscription journal which can lead to the misperception that they are of lower quality.
- If a researcher has paid a fee to publish, this can be misperceived as a necessity rather than a choice to get their paper published at all.
- Publishers invest in ethics checks and other quality assurance steps, and so publishers with less revenue can be misperceived as having to cut corners.
- OA journals are sometimes focused on volume of publishing, which can be seen as a conflict of interest between quantity and quality.
- OA publishing can sometimes be conflated with predatory publishing.
- ECRs can have negative perceptions about OA publishing because they cannot afford APCs.
- Established researchers can be biased in favor of journals they already know.

Researchers do need to trust and value open access journals and can in most cases. Participants suggested actions that OASPA and its members can take to address the perceptions about OA:

- Education and training are needed, including campaigns aimed at educating senior researchers and university leaders through data.
 - This is an area in which funders, librarians, and publishers can cooperate.
 - Use data to change the conversation and challenge misperceptions. Data from cOAlition S shows that funded researchers publish more articles in born-OA journals than in subscription titles. For example, of the “top 10” (by volume) journals used by Wellcome Trust authors in 2022, 8 of them were fully OA journals. Looking across all cOAlition S funders, seven out of the top 10 journals used by funded authors were native, fully OA journals.
 - An industry-wide study to compare the quality of journals that have transitioned to OA vs being born OA could establish if there was any difference.
 - Publishers should be very careful about how they use impact factor metrics, providing clear definitions and limitations about their use. Impact Factors sometimes reflect the quality and sometimes are a distortion of it.
 - Provide a toolkit to help publishers measure and communicate new metrics advocated by [COARA](#) and [DORA](#).
 - OASPA could raise awareness of its role in kite marking good processes and trusted journals. Good editorial practices, rigorous peer review, retraction policies, investments to screen for malpractice, etc. of course apply to all scholarly publications and not only OA publications.
- Change the discourse to promote trust as a valued form of prestige. Trust is built up through consistent quality assurance practices.
 - Publishers need to uphold and champion publishing standards for all types of titles.

- Be transparent about quality assurance practices and publishing standards so that researchers can make informed choices. Quality metrics about journal processes relevant to individual disciplines could be helpful. DOAJ provides a very useful service here for fully OA titles.
- Quality assurance in the process of scientific peer review must be clearly separated from the processes associated with the provision of publishing services to prevent practices that lower standards to increase publisher revenue. Editorial independence must be guaranteed and demonstrable.
- Encourage a culture of continuous quality development by publishers.
- It could be helpful to develop a system to evaluate how well a journal publisher aligns and works effectively with the values of libraries.
- The Code of Conduct says “Members must not indulge in any practices or activities that OASPA feels could bring the Association or open access publishing into disrepute. Misconduct may be reported to the Board of Directors and will be investigated according to a set procedure.” The Board may wish to review this part of the Code of Conduct and whether it is working as intended or whether it needs to be revised.
- Work together to challenge the status quo.
 - Indexing services discriminate against newer journals and multilingual publications. This privileges traditional journals and creates challenges for diversity, equity, and inclusion. This is perhaps an issue that could be addressed in partnership with DOAJ.
 - Publishers cannot change the tenure and promotion system but could advocate that it should be changed.
 - COARA and DORA might be good partners to explore how scholars might be evaluated differently.
 - Coordinate outreach and marketing with and through publishers to try and address perceived quality issues.
 - Perhaps the Code of Conduct might more clearly address the imperative of academic self-governance in scholarly publishing. This point was made in the Final Statement of the 16th Berlin Open Access Conference.
 - OASPA could build on the joint OASPA-UNESCO recommendations and set out new ways or metrics to measure impact and quality based on practices/processes rather than another notion of prestige.
 - Funder requirements to publish OA can and do help to change perceptions.

What are the pathways to stable and predictable funding streams for fully OA publishers?

We pivoted topics in the second half of the workshop. We began with a Slido poll asking participants how essential for global equity are funding models completely decoupled from articles and article numbers. The reason for this is that APCs and other models coupled to articles or article numbers were identified at earlier workshops as a significant barrier to equity. The chart below shows that although 13% thought this was not essential, most participants thought it somewhat or very essential. We repeated this poll at the end of the session, and the response was very much the same with the same average score of 3.6.

☆ 1 - How essential for global equity are funding models completely decoupled from articles and article numbers?

Rating Poll 23 votes 23 participants

slido

We then asked participants to discuss how publishers could find predictable, sustainable pathways to full OA outside of APC-driven routes or models tied to article numbers. We asked participants to suspend any disbelief they might feel that this could or should be the future, and to help us work on the pathways to funding in a fully OA world without those options. One participant neatly summarized the reason: article volumes will continue to grow with the democratization of research and to be sustainable for customers/stakeholders we need entirely fresh, affordable ways to cope with this at scale.

Publishers were encouraged to:

- Create opportunities for closer communications and engagement with libraries, funders, and researchers about their publishing/business models.
- Learn from the successful ways other publishers have achieved a full transition. Examples include subsidy models, collective models, membership models, crowdfunding, Subscribe to Open, and choreographed models like SCOAP3.
- Not think about any single business model in isolation, but instead mix and match. Different journals and authors in different parts of the world may need different combinations of business models.
- Think about pricepoints that are globally equitable.
- Reduce costs and unnecessary overheads where possible.
- Don't cut too deep: recognize that there are real costs and these need to be born as well as generating sufficient surplus.
- Think about the costs that will be removed from your operations if you were to shift to diamond OA, for example, and no longer need to administer transactional payments.
- Differentiate the costs you incur to publish from costs of other activities traditionally funded through publishing income.

- Recognize that becoming more equitable may have costs, and these – and how they are funded - need to be transparent to customers/stakeholders.

To support publishers, libraries and funders were encouraged to:

- Divert money to new OA models and initiatives that are not funded through APCs and where prices are not set in per-article terms.
- SCOSS and similar funding sources could be made available to publishers upon application.
- There may be a need for an affordable, independent clearing house to facilitate payments from libraries to publishers.
- Don't eliminate APCs entirely: they sometimes have a role to play and could be justified perhaps as an exception if not the norm.
- cOAlition S could encourage funders and universities to set aside part of their budgets to fund diamond OA and publishing platforms.

What equity issues might arise if publishers find these routes to be unavailable, and how might that impact and influence the scholarly publishing landscape?

Progress in removing subscription paywalls must not create barriers to participation in open science and scholarship. The open access transition must be inclusive and reflect the plurality of research disciplines, topics, languages, and outputs. A one-size-fits-all open access publishing model based on publishing charges is inequitable.

There are challenges faced by **smaller publishers** that are not challenges for larger publishers. These equity challenges include:

- A lack of communication, marketing, and sales resources.
- More limited array of internal skillsets.
- Not knowing who their own customers are as this information is only available to agents or aggregators.

Support that could help smaller publishers overcome challenges:

- There is a helpful role that library consortia can play by advocating with their members on behalf of smaller publishers who seek to transition fully to OA.
- Small publishers might benefit from special funding or support to transition the last 20% of their portfolio to full OA.
- Publishing platforms and other shared resources or support mechanisms funded by libraries and the research community (e.g., DIAMAS, Erudit, OJS, Redalyc, SciELO) could be helpful pathways or shared tools for submissions or editing. This could be conducive to cost reduction.

OASPA could help by providing exposure and visibility through its website or by other methods. Communications and marketing are both crucial, and expensive.

A library participant noted a sense of urgency to figure out how to get grant funding to support the more equitable models such as Subscribe to Open. A large portion of library acquisitions budgets are locked up in agreements with relatively few publishers. So, although there is money in the system to support other publishing models, it is challenging to free it up to use in an optimal fashion.

Funders might need to perceive 'trust signals' from publishers to feel reassured. Trust signals include globally equitable pricing, transparency, prices commensurate with services, and other conditions associated with Plan S. [cOAlition S, in partnership with Jisc and PLOS, are seeking to establish a multi-stakeholder working group to identify business models and arrangements that enable equitable participation in knowledge-sharing.](#)

OASPA might need to convene a cross-stakeholder conversation to evolve principles for OA agreements between libraries and publishers so that equity is at their heart. OASPA more broadly has a convening function and also a kitemarking function, a clearing house function, and an amplifying function which might be used, for example, to identify shared infrastructure requirements or opportunities.

*Equity is not just about publishing articles, participation is key to equity,
particularly for those previously excluded.*

Participants

The following people participated in this workshop. Please note that this does not mean they agree with all the points made in the workshop.

Joanna Ball (DOAJ, UK)
Sara Ball (UKRI, UK)
Sara Bosshart (Royal Society of Chemistry, UK)
Curtis Brundy (Iowa State University, USA)
Colleen Campbell (Max Planck Digital Library, Germany)
Paula Clemente Vega (Open Library for the Humanities)
Rod Cookson (IWA Publishing, UK)
Matt Day (Cambridge University Press, UK)
Scott Delman (ACM, USA)
Michael Donaldson (Canadian Science Publishing, Canada)
Lorraine Estelle (Information Power, UK)
Nasra Gathoni (Agha Khan University, Kenya)
Matt Giampoala (American Geophysical Union, AGU)
Saray Córdoba González (Universidade de Costa Rica - Costa Rica)
Kazuhiro Hayashi (National Institute of Science and Technology Policy, Japan)
Hannah Hope (Wellcome Trust, UK)
Phil Hurst (Royal Society, UK)

Andrew Joseph (Wits University Press, South Africa)
Robert Kiley (cOAlition S, UK)
Sharla Lair (Lyrisis, USA)
Malavika Legge (OASPA, UK)
Nick Lindsay (MIT Press)
Claire Moulton (The Company of Biologists, UK)
Grace Msoffe (University of Dodoma, Tanzania)
Susan Murray (African Journals Online)
Ritsuko Nakajima (JST)
Niamh O'Connor (PLOS, UK)
Wendy Patterson (Beilstein Institut, Germany)
Frances Pinter (CEU Press, Hungary)
Lucy Robinson (Sage, UK)
Johan Rooryck (cOAlition S, Belgium)
Ellen Tise (Stellenbosch University, South Africa)
Jessica Tucker (NIH)
Wynand Van der Walt (Rhodes University, South Africa)
Alicia Wise (Information Power, UK)

About OASPA (<https://oaspa.org/>)

Representing a diverse community of organisations engaged in open scholarship, OASPA works to encourage and enable open access as the predominant model of communication for scholarly outputs. We are committed to our mission of developing and disseminating solutions that advance open access and ensuring a diverse, vibrant, and healthy open access community.

About Information Power (<https://www.informationpower.co.uk/>)

Information Power Ltd is a woman-owned microbusiness based in the UK. We have provided consultancy services in the research information space since 2006. We bring together bespoke teams of consultants with diverse, yet complementary, backgrounds and skills to provide support that spans the spectrum of challenges facing research funders, libraries, and publishers. Together we specialise in engagement on sensitive issues including business strategies and open access policy and practice.

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